

DESIGN AND STRUCTURAL FEASIBILITY STUDY OF A LIGHTWEIGHT FLOOR SYSTEM FOR RENOVATION

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Abstract

An increasing number of outdated floors will need to be renovated in the coming years. Existing floor solutions with stay-in-place formworks are often composed of heavy elements which complicate their applicability in renovations. To meet this increasing demand and allow at the same time manoeuvrability and a facilitation of the construction process, we designed a new lightweight floor solution.

This paper describes the conceptual design and a preliminary calculation to check the structural feasibility. Composite-concrete beams with sandwich panels in between are the main components of a floor system which weighs 34% less than traditional beam and block systems and stays under the deflection requirements of $L/250$. This paper proves the potential of composite materials in floor slabs and even more the suitability of this lightweight concept for renovation purposes.

1 Introduction

Renovation and reconversion are a growing activity within the construction industry. The urban population growth in the years ahead will only stimulate people even more to renovate outdated buildings. The patrimony of cities already consists of a high number of outdated buildings, which cannot provide adequate housing functionalities and are often vacant. The renewal of the existing patrimony can be done in two ways: construction of new buildings or renovation of outdated buildings. The renovation of existing buildings to adequate housing is (i) the fastest way to provide available housing, and (ii) a far more sustainable option than new construction: the re-use of most of the existing structure allows us to reduce the carbon footprint of

the construction industry significantly. On top of this, renovation allows a city to retain the already limited free space and to limit the nuisance for the habitants. The increasing demand and the specific supply requirements of renovations create opportunities for new building solutions specially designed for and adapted to the renovation context.

The renovation sector needs its own, adapted building solutions. Therefore, this paper proposes a new floor concept that anticipates on the growing renovation market by developing renovation-specific building elements, which encourage the renovation of buildings. The main focus of this research lies on the design of a floor slab which facilitates the construction process by a minimization of the weight of the individual components. Therefore this concept will combine the manoeuvrability of a beam and block system with the lightweight advantages of composite materials. The applicability of the concept will be focussed on the replacement of wooden floors in outdated buildings and the creation of additional floors in between existing storeys. Section 4.1 describes this conceptual design. In section 4.2, a preliminary calculation has been performed to validate the structural feasibility of this advanced concept.

2 SiP formworks

2.1 SiP formwork concepts for concrete slabs

Few concrete floor systems exist today that are adapted to the specific requirements within renovation context. Nowadays, different kinds of Stay-in-Place (SiP) formworks for concrete slabs can be distinguished. Lattice girder floors or half slabs (Fig. 1) are often used as SiP formwork for slabs cast on-site. A concrete overlay is finally cast on top of the formwork to provide the total bending

stiffness of the slab. Although this high-quality product has a rapid on-site installation, the disadvantages of the high weight and difficult manoeuvrability make them unsuitable for renovation purposes.

A more renovation-friendly alternative for these lattice girder floors are the so-called beam and block floors (Fig. 2 and Fig. 3). This semi-prefabricated floor system is today's most used floor system for renovation purposes. Small building blocks, usually made from terracotta, concrete or lightweight materials, are positioned between inverted T-beams. These smaller individual construction elements facilitate on-site placing and reduce the use of heavy machinery. Despite the reduced weight of components, the transport mass per square meter is comparable to that of a half slab (100 kg/m² [1], Tab. 1). Moreover, the weight of these individual components remains rather high and the installation is labour intensive, making beam and block slabs a relatively expensive floor solution.

As half slabs and – to a lesser extent - beam and block systems have the disadvantage of being heavy, one searches for lighter SiP alternatives such as steel and composite SiP slab formworks. Steel slab formworks (Fig. 4) are composed of a thin metal sheet, shaped in such a way to provide sufficient stiffness, and a concrete layer which is cast on-site. Unfortunately, the use of steel formworks can also cause some problems. Corrosion problems can occur [2] due to the exposure of the metal surface to moist conditions. Furthermore, an adhesion problem between the smooth surface of the steel plate and concrete prevents the composite action of the slab [3].

The above mentioned disadvantages clearly state the need for other lightweight SiP slab solutions. To combine properties like strength and stiffness, but still remain lightweight, composite materials were introduced. Composites have already proven their usefulness in the aerospace and car industry. But thanks to advantages in the field of transportation and corrosive environments, the use of composites can also benefit the construction industry.

2.2 State of the art of composite SiP formwork concepts for beams and slabs

The use of a beam and block system as starting point for the basic concept requires a present state of the art overview of hybrid slab and beam designs.

In the past, FRP SiP slab formworks have been often used for the construction of bridge decks. In 1990, Hillman and Murray can be considered as one of the first authors to propose a slab with a pultruded FRP SiP formwork [4]. Following their example, similar concepts [5, 2] were developed and applied for bridge constructions.

Different concepts of hybrid beams – composed out of a compressive concrete layer and FRP (Fibre Reinforced Polymer) tensile reinforcement – have been studied by different authors: Deskovic et al [6], Canning et al [7], van Erp et al [8], Hulat et al [9], Correia et al [10], Chakraborty et al [11] (Fig. 5) and Remy [12]. Today's research is mainly focussed on the behaviour of hardened hybrid beams. As a result, most of the mentioned examples are not suited for casting on-site. O. Remy [12] (Fig. 6) focussed both on the wet and hardened stage and proposed a new structural SiP formwork concept for beams.

The idea to use composite materials to create lightweight elements (easy placement) which even contribute to the hardened phase (elimination of steel reinforcement) will be the starting point for the research towards a new floor system concept. Problems with fire safety of FRP composites are solved in this concept by using fire safe materials such as cement composites.

3 Composites for structural applications

For the design of a new lightweight stand-alone floor system, the authors of this paper smartly combined Fibre Reinforced Polymers (Fig. 7) and Textile Reinforced Cements (TRC). The high fibre volume fraction of FRP composites results in a high specific strength and stiffness. These properties make them very suitable for structural SiP formworks as they can not only reduce weight of formworks, but also substitute the traditional longitudinal steel reinforcement in a concrete

element [6, 7, 8]. Unfortunately, the application of polymer composites in civil constructions is restrained because of fire safety issues. In the presented design, TRC composites are proposed as a solution to these fire safety problems. As a consequence, CFRP (Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer) composites will be used inside the floor slab, while TRC composites are used at the outer surface to ensure the material fire safety of the floor system.

Cementitious materials are stiff and strong materials in compression, but in turn, they lack sufficient tensile strength and have a brittle behaviour. The costs to improve the tensile behaviour can be limited by the use of E-glass fibres which are less expensive compared to carbon fibres. However, the inability to impregnate high volumes of discontinuous fibres [13, 14] limited their structural application and has led to the use of fibre textiles and thus Textile Reinforced Cement. Moreover, low-cost E-glass fibres can not be used as fibre reinforcement without a significant degradation of the tensile strength due to the alkaline environment of ordinary Portland cement [15].

To avoid these shortcomings, researchers at the Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) have developed an Inorganic Phosphate Cement (IPC) [16], which is acidic in fresh state, but pH neutral after hardening. The relatively small grain size of IPC (between 10 and 100 μ m) enables the impregnation of dense textiles which results in a uniform fibre distribution and a higher fibre volume fraction. As a result, glass fibre reinforced IPC (GFR.IPC) can achieve fibre volume fractions up to 25% (Fig. 8) [17]). Hence, TRC composites with a significant tensile strength are the state of the art today. When reinforced with randomly oriented glass fibre textiles, the IPC matrix has a tensile capacity of 60 MPa and a compressive capacity of 80 MPa. The linear behaviour in compression clearly differs from the quasi bilinear behaviour in tension (Fig. 8). After cracking of the brittle cement matrix, the fibres are forced to take up all the tensile forces, resulting in an initial un-cracked stage (E-modulus = 19 GPa), and a cracked stage with reduced stiffness (3.75 GPa for 18 fibre volume % [18]). GFR.IPC has already proven its capabilities as an appropriate material for structural stay-in-place formworks [19, 20, 21].

4 A Lightweight SiP (L.SiP) formwork for slabs

4.1 Concept

In this section, the authors propose the structural L.SiP formwork that consists of hybrid concrete – composite beams and lightweight sandwich panels, suitable for on-site assembly. Conform the beam and block concept, the sandwich panels are positioned in between the beams, after which a concrete layer is poured on top of them to create a monolithic floor (Fig. 12).

To make sure that the hybrid beams have a sufficient strength and stiffness in relation to the weight during casting, the authors have chosen to integrate an internal element inside the hybrid beam (Fig. 10). For the most part, this element can be made out of GFRP (Glass Fibre Reinforced Polymer). Preliminary calculations have shown the necessity of additional stiff materials to provide the necessary bending stiffness. Adding CFRP at the bottom increases the bending stiffness significantly, but the adding becomes less efficient by the downward shifting of the neutral axis. To counteract this downward shift a low cost material such as high strength concrete is used at the upper side of the internal element. In this way, a hollow – and thus lightweight – internal element is designed to provide the bending stiffness for the beam.

Besides the amount of CFRP, also the shape of this internal element is of great importance. Some first calculations (paragraph 4.2) have been made with a rectangular cross section. Using such a rectangular cross section enables us to use existing composite profiles. In the future, a further optimization may be performed to eliminate as much as possible concrete in tension. After all, concrete in tension can be neglected for the force equilibrium. As a consequence, reducing this volume has almost no structural influence, but allows us to reduce the final weight significantly. While changing the shape, one constraint must be taken into account: the shape may not hinder the flow of concrete during casting stage. A hindered flow can create inclusions in the concrete with the consequent low strength characteristics.

The shape of the outer formwork of the beam depends on the chosen way of connecting the beams

and the sandwich panels. This paragraph proposes two possibilities to connect these elements. In a first proposition (Fig. 9), the well-known shape of inverted T-beams is maintained so the panels can be positioned in between them from above. This type of beams will be part of the bottom side of the floor system, so this outer formwork will be made out of GFR.IPC to ensure the material fire safety. A second proposition (Fig. 10) is to shape the outer formwork as an open thin cylinder which offers certain in-section flexibility. For this purpose, the flexibility of a thin GFR.IPC section can be used. This choice of geometry allows us to create a fast connection of the sandwich elements in between the parallel beams from below. Insertion of the sandwich panels from below will certainly facilitate the construction process, but at the same time also make it more complicated. The outer skin of the beams must be flexible (Fig. 11) to allow easy snapping but also robust enough to avoid de-snapping.

To serve as lightweight filling blocks, sandwich panels are chosen for their high stiffness-to-weight ratio. Only a small concrete layer on top of these sandwich panels is required to achieve an optimal hybrid material use. The bottom facing of the sandwich panel will be made out of GFR.IPC for fire safety issues, while the upper facing material can be chosen according to the required mechanical properties. To retain lightweight elements, one can choose to use foam in between the facings or even a corrugated structure.

The construction process of this floor system (with the circular outer formwork of the beams) can be summarized in the following steps: Hybrid beams with FRP core and TRC outer formwork (Fig. 12i) are carefully placed next to each other at equal distances. After fixing the beams, sandwich panels with TRC faces (Fig. 12ii) are snapped in place. First, the beams are cast (Fig. 12iii) to provide the needed bearing capacity for the top layer of concrete. In a second phase, the concrete top layer is cast (Fig. 12iv).

4.2 Design calculations

A first design calculation is performed by the authors to prove the feasibility of the concept. This study checks a 5-m-span slab (Fig. 13) as an example of frequently used spans in renovation of single family houses.

The internal GFR.IPC element with a thickness of 2 mm has a width of 70 mm and a height of 155 mm. At the bottom side, a carbon layer with a thickness of 2 mm increases the bending stiffness. At the upper side, a high strength concrete layer of 20 mm is used to keep the neutral axis in the middle. This stiff element limits the deflection of the 2 mm thick cylindrical outer formwork of the support beams. The distance between two parallel support beams is 600 mm, while the beams themselves have a width of 200 mm. The sandwich panels have a height of 180 mm and the compressive concrete layer equals 45 mm, resulting in a total floor slab height of 225 mm. All material properties are assumed to be linear elastic. The high strength concrete has a stiffness of 50 GPa, the on-site cast concrete 30 GPa, GFRP 16.8 GPa and the CFRP strip 240 GPa.

In order to bear a final service load of 3.50 kN/m², two casting stages and one serviceability state are considered. In a first stage (casting 1), the outer formwork of the beams is filled with concrete. In a second stage (casting 2), the entire hardened beam has sufficient load bearing capacity to carry the weight of the top compressive concrete layer. After casting, the hybrid slab weighs 165 kg/m². For casting 1 only the bending stiffness of the internal element is considered (Fig. 14 a). For casting 2 the contribution of the additional concrete in compression is added (Fig. 14 b). At serviceability limit state the authors only took a width of 300 mm of the compressive layer into account (Fig. 14 c).

At every casting stage, the bending stiffness (Tab. 2) of the loadbearing components (GFRP profile, CFRP strip and concrete layer) is calculated to determine the position of the neutral axis. Together with the casting stage loads, these properties allow us to calculate the deflection. Within the assumptions of Bernoulli and a perfect bond between all materials, the deflections under casting and service loads must remain below the SLS

requirements of $L/250$ ($=20\text{mm}$). The deflections during the first and second casting stage remain limited to respectively 8.9 mm and 11.1 mm. Thanks to the limited deflections, the use of additional supports during casting becomes even superfluous. Finally, the service load causes a total deflection of 12.2 mm ($<L/250$). An Ultimate Limit State (ULS) check reveals a load bearing capacity of 14.6 kN/m^2 and thus a maximum service load of 7 kN/m^2 .

The use of lightweight elements (6 kg/m for the composite beams and 20 kg/m for the sandwich elements) results in a low transport mass of about 30 kg/m^2 . This floor concept includes clearly a big reduction ($>70\%$, Tab. 1) of the transport weight in comparison with traditional block and beam systems (Tab. 1).

5 Conclusions

Three components – beams, sandwich panels and a concrete top layer – form together a new lightweight SiP formwork for slabs. Strengthened by its excellent fire resistant capacities, cement composites can offer the required material characteristics for future floor slabs. Nevertheless, this design smartly combines FRP composites and cement composites to obtain the necessary strength and stiffness without losing the lightweight aspect.

The new concept weighs 57% less than traditional on-site cast concrete floors and 34% less than beam and block systems. This weight decrease refers not only to the self weight of the slab, but also to the individual formwork elements (and thus installation and transportation weight). A concrete layer of 45 mm is sufficient to bear the service loads and limit the deflections to the specified values. The results of this structural feasibility study show a great potential for composite materials in concrete floor slabs and inspires future research.

Fig. 1: Lattice girder slabs are one of the most used concrete SiP formworks for floor construction. The weight and dimensions limit the application within the renovation industry. [22]

Fig. 2: A traditional beam and block system, consisting of inverted concrete T-beams and in between placed concrete building blocks. [23]

Fig. 3: Traditional concrete beams are reinforced with steel rebars at the bottom (tension) side. The filling blocks can be hollow, but only consist of concrete.

	L.SiP slab	Beam & Block Slab	half slab
elements (kg/m ²)	30	100	120
casted concrete (kg/m ²)	135	150	264
total slab weight (kg/m ²)	165	250	384

Tab. 1 The installation weight of a beam and block slab and a half slab are comparable. The L.SiP formwork leads to a installation weight reduction of at least 70% in comparison with traditional floor slabs.

Fig. 4: A metal SiP formwork sheet is shaped in a trapezoidal shape to offer sufficient bending stiffness. [24]

Fig. 5: The cross-section of a hybrid beam, proposed by A. Chakraborty. [11]

Fig. 6: A new lightweight SiP formwork concept for beams by O. Remy. [12]

Fig. 7: The good mechanical properties of composites are the result of strong and stiff fibres. [25]

Fig. 8: The stress-strain diagram of TRC with random oriented glass fibres mats and an inorganic phosphate cement matrix. [26]

Fig. 9: An inverted T-support beam with a GFR.IPC skin and a CFRP strip at the bottom. The concrete filling blocks are replaced by sandwich panels.

Fig. 10: A circular outer formwork is used for the support beams.

Fig. 11: The thin GFR.IPC outer skin has the requested flexibility to allow easy snapping.

Fig. 12 Lightweight floor elements (ii) are clicked between the hybrid beam (i) elements. The concrete is then cast in the beams (iii) and on top of the floor elements (iv).

Fig. 13: The dimensions of the considered floor slab.

Fig. 14: An overview of the different sections for the casting stages (a, b) and the serviceability state (c).

	Casting 1	Casting 2	Use
Height NA [mm]	105	121	145
$EI_{GFR,P \text{ profile}}$ [Nmm ²]	5,1E+10	7,0E+10	1,1E+11
$EI_{CFR,P \text{ strip}}$ [Nmm ²]	2,6E+11	3,4E+11	4,9E+11
$EI_{\text{concrete L.SiP}}$ [Nmm ²]	1,3E+11	4,8E+10	2,7E+09
$EI_{\text{concrete 1}}$ [Nmm ²]	x	1,8E+10	x
$EI_{\text{concrete 2}}$ [Nmm ²]	x	x	2,2E+11
Deflection [mm]	8,9	11,1	12,2

Tab. 2: The deflections of the three different states

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